

Database of the Collaboration between an artist and an architect

(final report)

Information about this document

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Abstract: After the February coup in 1948 in Czechoslovakia, the Communist Party came to power, which gradually nationalized all private property and began to control public and cultural life, including the installation of works of art in architecture. In this way, it gradually continued the activities that were mainly carried out by the bourgeoisie before World War II. We have records of some of this activity in the annually published inventories called "Collaboration of an artist with an architect", which record individual works of art placed as part of the implementation of architectural orders in the territory of former Czechoslovakia and abroad. These printed volumes, depicting the installation of architecture between 1972 and 1989, are a welcome source of information about art not only for academia but also for enthusiasts from both contemporary republics. Precisely for this reason, we proceeded to digitize these hard-to-find works and convert them into a structured database, which now contains over sixteen thousand records. If the original database was sorted only by municipality, the current database also allows searching for works by author, investor, or other criteria. In addition to searching, it is also a good substrate for further research in this area.

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Introduction

Although the installation of art in architecture is nothing new and has been done since the beginning of human cultural history, the purpose of art has changed, as has the donor. Thus, in the 20th century, the influence of private donors from among industrialists and the nobility began to decline, and the state began to assert itself as the main sponsor of artists creating for the architecture. First, this principle appeared in the United States as early as in the 1930s in the form of a regulation that required allocating one percent of completed state construction contracts to art. After the Second World War, it was taken over by the states of Western Europe and later in the mid-60s by the totalitarian Czechoslovakia.¹

As a result of nationalization, the Czechoslovak state became the only investor since the 1950s, and it also decided what kind of art and where it would be placed. However, it was not until 1965 that the principle of a percentage on art was enacted, exactly one to four percent on art.¹

Artworks for buildings were approved in the form of tenders or in competitions.¹ Regional *Commissions for cooperation between artists and architects*² of the Czech, and Slovak Funds for Visual Arts (CFFVA and SFFVA)¹ decided on a number of projects, but not on all of them. For example, the artistic decoration of the Zlín Municipal Theater was decided by a commission established by the council of the Municipal National Committee.³

The Funds were created in the mid-1950s on the basis of Copyright Act No. 115⁴ – the oldest meeting of the commission was documented in 1956.²

There are stacks of records in the Czech archives about the implementations that went through the meetings of the regional *Commissions of collaboration between the artist and the architect* (hereinafter referred to as the *Commission*). However, they are unprocessed and may take several years for archivists to process them. Nevertheless, some are accessible under the supervision of archivists.

Another source of information on works of art in architecture published by the Commission, or by the Czech Fund for Visual Arts' enterprise Dílo, are the printed inventories entitled *Spolupráce výtvarníka s architektem* (in English *Collaboration between an artist and an architect*; hereinafter referred to as *Collaboration*) published every year between 1972–1989. The list is sorted by the regions of the time, and from 1984 regions were removed so municipalities were listed alphabetically.⁵ Unfortunately, they do not contain all

¹ Karous, Pavel (2019). "Umění v hotelu ČSSR; Systém osazování výtvarného umění v architektuře na Západě a v ČSSR". In Karous, Pavel (ed.). *Hotel Praha* (in Czech). Prague: BiggBoss; Academy of Arts, Architecture and Design in Prague; Galerie výtvarného umění Cheb. pp. 60–73. ISBN 978-80906817-9-8.

² Říhová, Vladislava; Křenková, Zuzana (2016). "[Archivní fondy podniku Českého fondu výtvarných umění Dílo](#)" (PDF). *Opuscula historiae artium*: 104–119.

³ Drábková, Veronika (2017). "[Výtvarná scéna ve Zlíně v 60. letech](#)". Prague: Univerzita Karlova. p 53.

⁴ CFFVA is recorded in the literature in 1954 (Bibliografický katalog ČSR. Prague: Národní knihovna, 1954. P. 2242) and SFFVA a year later in 1955 (Výbor svazu architektů: Usnesení výboru svazu architektů. In: *Architektura ČSR*. Praha: Klub architektů, 1955, č. 6. ISSN 0300-5305. P. 204.

⁵ Říhová, Vladislava; Křenková, Zuzana (2018). "[Metodika archivního průzkumu uměleckých děl druhé poloviny 20. století ve veřejném prostoru](#)" (PDF).

the production captured by CFFVA and SFFVA of that time,⁶ and sometimes, on the contrary, they mention one work more than once.⁷

Despite the fact that all printed lists of the Collaboration are not available in any archive or library, they have become a welcome source of information about the art in architecture of the period in question for a number of academics and enthusiasts.⁸ We can find numerous references to them in the Internet databases *Sochy a města*,⁸ *Vetřelci a volavky*,⁹ or the Czech version of Wikipedia.¹⁰

It is precisely for the above-mentioned reason that we focused on the digitization of the Collaboration printed forms as part of this project. An inventory in digital form can provide quick access to the given information, but also the basis for further research.

The Collaboration periodicals

As already mentioned in the Introduction, there is no complete series of the Collaboration in any Czech library or an archive.¹¹ As of November 2023, not even the inventories have been digitized in the National Digital Library. So they exist in printed form and are scattered in various libraries and archives. The following description therefore refers to samples stored in the National Library of the Czech Republic and in the library of the Museum of Applied Arts in Prague.

Individual prints are A5 size paperback with soft boards. The early years contained fewer entries, so they have a notebook format that is stapled in the middle with a metal clip, in later years the metal clip remains, but the spine is still taped and the boards are glued to it. In one case, we found a defect in the form of a poorly trimmed side that was larger than the others.

All the notebooks examined had printed boards and inner pages. The samples contain only text and no images, the only exception being the logo of the Dílo enterprise. The first periodicals had the plates printed in light blue, the others only in black. The paper is white or yellowish and contains clearly visible particles. The language used is Czech and the

⁶ An example is the sculpture *Ležící* (in English *Lying*) from 1982 located in the atrium of the former trade and service center in Stará Osada, Brno, the Czech Republic, which is not in the list of Collaboration, but there is a record of it in the archive funds of the CFFVA. See: <https://sochyamesta.cz/zaznam/19875>

⁷ For example, the work *Rodina* (in English *Family*) by the sculptor Sylva Lacinová, located on the housing estate in Opava-Kateřinky, is listed three times. In 1978 and twice in 1980. The occurrence in two years may mean that the work reached the Commission's meeting twice, and the double occurrence in one year, in turn, that the materials provided for the Collaboration were supplied by different administrators and the work was not systematic (as stated by Říhová, 2018).

⁸ Říhová, Vladislava; Křenková, Zuzana (2016). "[Archivní fondy podniku Českého fondu výtvarných umění Dílo](#)" (PDF). *Opuscula historiae artium*: 104–119.

⁹ Especially on the project website: <https://www.vetrelciavolavky.cz/>. Collaboration is also used to determine the works that appear in the Facebook group Vetřelci a volavky - public art of the socialist era: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/372485406179>.

¹⁰ Especially thanks to Jaroslava Juklíčková's project Documentation of Endangered Monuments.

¹¹ Říhová, Vladislava; Křenková, Zuzana (2018). "[Metodika archivního průzkumu uměleckých děl druhé poloviny 20. století ve veřejném prostoru](#)" (PDF).

included works are from all over Czechoslovakia and from abroad. The Slovak part, however, is completely missing in several parts (see Table 1). Individual pages are numbered.

Table 1. Structure of records, representation of individual parts, more detailed division

For year	Sorting method	Czechia	Slovakia	Foreign placement	Detailed division of Prague
1972	regions	yes	yes	no	no
1973	regions	yes	yes	yes	no
1974	regions	yes	yes	no	no
1975	regions	yes	no	no	yes
1976	regions	yes	no	yes	yes
1977	regions	yes	no	yes	yes
1978	regions	yes	no	yes	yes
1979	regions	yes	no	yes	yes
1980	regions	yes	no	yes	yes
1981	regions	yes	no	yes	yes
1982	regions	yes	no	yes	yes
1983	regions	yes	only Bratislava	yes	yes
1984	alphabetically	yes	yes	no	no
1985	alphabetically	yes	yes	yes	no
1986	alphabetically	yes	yes	yes	no
1987	alphabetically	yes	no	yes	yes
1988	alphabetically	yes	yes	yes	yes
1989	alphabetically	yes	yes	yes	yes

The information is therefore contained on the cover and further inside, where it is divided into a preface, table of contents, and the inventory database itself. Additional technical information is scattered between the boards and previously mentioned sections. The cover print varies slightly from year to year. In the 1970s, it was initially printed in blue and also contained the logo of the Dílo enterprise, which is a small white letter "d" on a blue background with the inscription DÍLO below it. One of the prints also had this logo on the spine.¹²

A short preface covering up to two pages is located behind the opening page and contains most often information about art in architecture and the activities of the Dílo enterprise. It is always signed Dílo, an enterprise of the Czech Foundation for Visual Arts. The preface for the inventory for 1989 has a slightly different style, where the author complains about "the new economic situation and the increase in the prices of printing products" to which the inventory is adapted. Visually, this inventory already looks different, a different font is used, and this part, for example, does not contain capital letters for the headings of individual

¹² Year 1975.

sections. From the preface of this edition, it could therefore be concluded that it was published after the fall of communism in 1989.

Between 1972 and 1983, a short table of contents is given at the end,¹³ which divides the publication into an Introduction and then a division by individual regions, where the name of the region or locality is on the left (e.g. Prague, or Foreign Placements) and on the right is the range of pages on which this inventory is found. In the publication for 1984, however, Dílo stopped sorting the realizations by region, and so the table of contents is not included anymore.

As for the structure of the database itself, between 1972 and 1983 it was divided by region, with Prague and foreign placements having their own separate sections. These sections are not arranged in alphabetical order, but usually start with Prague, then follow Foreign Placements, then the Central Bohemian Region, and then other regions. Alphabetical order is followed within the individual sections and if there is more than one implementation under one municipality, the inscription of the municipality is not repeated more than once. In some cases, the division is more detailed, for example in Prague 1–10 or Ostrava-Vítkovice or Ostrava-Poruba. Since 1984, the division by individual regions has been abolished and everything is sorted according to individual letters of the alphabet, foreign placements are prioritized. In some years, there are no records of Slovak or foreign placements. Even though the structure of the document varies throughout time, it doesn't make big difficulties to find and enter by its location. The overview is provided in Table 1.

The inventories do not contain much technical information. Annuals for the years 1972 to 1975 contain a brief imprint. We learn that the 72 and 73 volumes were compiled by Daniela Léblová, and the 74 volume by Olga Ambrožová. Wherever there is an imprint it is clearly stated that the publisher is DÍLO, the promotion department. Additional information on who printed the list are Středočeské tiskárny, division 19 (for 1974's inventory), TOMOS Praha (1980), and NADAS 02 (1986). *Ščt* is mentioned twice (1975 and 1976). The release dates are not known, but it is likely that the inventories were always published the following year, so if there are inventories for the years 1972–1989, the inventories would be published in the years 1973–1990.

The cover of the inventory for 1977, which is subtitled "Overview of works for the year 1976–1977; II. part", which forces one to look for part I. This volume contains a table of contents at the end, which is divided into two columns for 1976 numbered from page 1 to page 163, and for 1977 from page 165 to page 281. And indeed this volume is not numbered from one, but the first database page begins with the number 165. In checking the available copy for 1976, we find that the distribution of the inventory corresponds to the content in the 1977 inventory. Moreover, it seems that the 1976 inventory was published in 1977 (since it contains *Ščt 17-2082/77*) and the 1977 inventory must therefore logically have been published in 1978. From this comparison, it follows that no I. part is missing and it is the one for the year 1976.

The text is readable by the eye with a minimum of typos or misspellings. The font used is unknown, but all but the last edition appear to use the same font, which resembles a Courier font. The latter contains a large amount of color so that the individual characteristics of the letters are sometimes bathed in color, which can cause poor readability for systems based on image recognition. On the other hand, the font used for

¹³ In the 1978 list, the table of contents is at the front.

the 1989 list is quite fine and machine-readable, but not as pleasing to the human eye as the previous one.

Results

The resulting digital database is not publicly available, but it is possible to obtain some data from it upon request to the author of this report. The reason is, on the one hand, the unresolved copyright side of the matter, and, on the other hand, the fact that it was acquired from private sources.

The results cannot be fully presented yet, as the database is in a state where it allows easy research, but does not allow for statistical analysis, as it has not yet been cleaned and individual items have not been linked to identifiers. After all, this should be part of the second part of the project, which is planned, but which cannot be implemented without cooperation with a partner-research institution.

Figure 1. Screenshot from the database of the Collaboration placed in a spreadsheet. The displayed tab divides the data into sections, as it was divided in the graphically presented structure of the printed Collaboration. Other tabs then divide the data further, creating opportunities for statistical evaluation.

1	Rok	Místo	Dílo	Investor	Stran
8174	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Art protis "Vlajkonoši" pro budovu KSC	KV KSC Ústí nad Labem	74
8175	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Kovaná okna pro státní hrad Střekov	Správa hradu Střekova Ústí nad Labem	74
8176	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Směrníky z umělé hmoty pro závodní jídelnu chemičky		74
8177	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Mosazná výtvarná madla na dveře pro závodní jídelnu chemičky		74
8178	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Keramický reliéf do haly závodní jídelny chemičky		74
8179	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Tři malované vitráže (sklo a olovo) pro salónek ředitele a p	Spolchemie Ústí nad Labem	74
8180	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Svítilna (sklo a mosaz) pro zasedací místnost INVA v Předlicích		74
8181	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Dekoratívni reliéf (litý hliník) pro vstupní halu INVA v Předlicích		75
8182	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Stukový reliéf "Symbol života" pro zasedací místnost INVA v	Výrobní družstvo invalidů Litoměřice	75
8183	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Kamenná plastika "Žena" v areálu nemocnice	Inženýrská organizace Ústí nad Labem	75
8184	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Skleněná mozaika pro ZDS na Kamenném vrchu	Pozemní stavby Ústí nad Labem	75
8185	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Goblén pro kancelář CKM	Cestovní kancelář mládeže Praha	75
8186	1980	Ústí nad Labem	Dřevěný reliéf pro prodejnu květin ve Fučíkově ul.	Zahradnický podnik Ústí nad Labem	75
12034	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Označení 36 provozoven ve Fučíkově ulici	Pozemní stavby, Ústí n. L., Velká Hradeb	120
12035	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Znak restaurace a kavárny "Merkur", hotel "Vladimir" ve F	Restaurace, Ústí n. L., Pařížská 20	120
12036	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Označení pivnice "Družba", Fučíkova 86	Restaurace, Ústí n. L., Pařížská 20	120
12037	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Skleněná mozaika v hale tělocvičny TJ Rudé hvězda v ulici	Krajská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n	121
12038	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Plastika "Gymnastka" - sádra, dřevo - ve vstupní hale těloc	Krajská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n	121
12039	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Plastika "Boxeři" - hliník, mosaz - na schodišti tělocvičny T	Krajská správa ministerstva vnitra, Ústí n	121
12040	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Plastická skleněná vitráž ve vstupní hale Krajského projek	Pozemní stavby, Ústí n. L., Velká Hradeb	121
12041	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Plastiky zvířat - umělá pryskyřice - "Dětský svět" v Zoo Ust	Zoologická zahrada, Ústí n. L., Svermova	121
12042	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Návrhy na firemní označení prodejen: Hedva, Klenoty, Bižu	Hedva, Moravská Třebová, Fučíkova 19	121
12043	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Pískovcová socha "Nový život" před střediskem občanské	Inženýrské organizace, Ústí n. L., ulice S	122
12044	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Triptych "Historie bojů dělnické třídy" - olej na plátně - ve foyeru budovy Krajské politické školy v Hoř		122
12045	1984	Ústí nad Labem	Triptych "Výstavba socialistické společnosti" - olej na platně - ve foyeru přednáškového sálu Krajské		122

Conclusion

In conclusion, it must be added that the current database is sufficient to speed up research and publication activity, however, the study based on data from the database brings new light into the area of interest. From the total number of 16,502 items, it can be assumed that the Collaboration contains only a slightly smaller number of works of art. As we are aware many are not included, Collaborations do not include the 1950s and 1960s, but also some of the works placed from the decision of other parties, the total number of artworks

in the architecture placed between 1950 and 1990 could reach 20,000 or more. Such a number of works would be the sufficient sample for further statistical analysis to understand the entire collection.